

Performance and innovative behavior of employees. Development and application of a measurement tool for workplace research

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Abstract

In an innovation driven and knowledge based economy, the success of an organization depends on the performance and innovative behavior of its employees. We develop a simple standardized questionnaire to measure three dimensions of performance (task performance, context performance, counterproductive behavior), and three dimensions of innovative behavior (idea generation, idea promotion and idea implementation). Based on existing scales from the literature we first made a long version of the questionnaire. We tested this version in a group of 1101 office workers from a large company, working in an open plan office. The measurements were performed twice, with a 3 month interval. Based on factor analyses and reliability analyses we propose a simplified version of the questionnaire that can be used in ergonomics research to measure self-perceived performance and innovative behavior. In the concise version of the questionnaire each of the six dimensions is measured by only three items, making it practically useful. We will discuss the advantages and disadvantages of using self-perception performance measures, and of using generalized questions that can be applied in any workplace. Furthermore we have applied the tool to explore the links between several physical work environment factors (e.g. crowding, noise, physical characteristics) and each dimension of performance and innovative behavior, and between several organisational work environment factors (e.g. job complexity, autonomy) and these dimensions. The results of these analyses were not yet available at the time of writing this abstract, but will be presented at the conference.